

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF CLASSROOM ENVIRONMENT, FAMILY TYPE AND SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Nayab Ali^{*1}, Shah Waheed Ghalib², Mushtaq Ahmad³, Javaria⁴, Asma Bibi⁵

^{*1}*Social Case Worker, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Child Protection and Welfare Commission (KPCPWC).*

²*Ph.D. Scholar, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan.*

³*Probation Officer, Directorate of Reclamation and Probation, Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.*

⁴*M.Phil. Scholar, Department of Sociology, University of Peshawar.*

⁵*M. Phil Sociology. Department of Rural Sociology, Agriculture University Peshawar.*

^{*1}nayabaup@gmail.com, ²sw.ghalibstd@uop.edu.pk, ³sociologistahmad@gmail.com, ⁴javeriakhan1990@gmail.com, ⁵asmabibi202@gmail.com

*10000-0003-0047-3556

Corresponding Author: *

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18219627>

ABSTRACT

The present study deals with the association classroom environment and students' academic achievement. Moreover, the study explored how classroom environments affect the academic achievement of students from varied socioeconomic background and various family types. A cross-sectional and purposive sampling technique was adopted to gather information from a sample of 448 students. Chi-square and Kendall's Tau-c (T^c) tests were used to determine the direction and strength of association between and among variables. The results established that students' academic achievement was significantly and positively associated with enough space for free and comfortable movement of students in the classroom ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.322$), proper lighting and ventilation system ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.260$), sufficient seating arrangements ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.167$), providing timely feedback to students ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.331$), and students' participation in class ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.348$). Furthermore, the results highlighted that both family type and socioeconomic status (SES) are significant contributors to students' academic achievement. The results show that when experiencing the same classroom environment, students from nuclear and higher socioeconomic standing families perform better academically than their counterparts.

Keywords: *academic achievement, classroom environment, family type, socioeconomic status.*

INTRODUCTION

Education produces academic achievement, which is typically tested by exams and indicates the degree to which students have achieved their desired behaviour in the classroom

(Harinarayanan and Pazhanivelu, 2018). Environmental and social settings at home and school, along with demographic and psychological factors, have an impact on students'

achievement (Singh et al, 2016). These settings can include physical spaces, such as classrooms and libraries, as well as social and emotional environments that affect students' learning experiences. Every classroom has its own distinctive teaching and learning conditions. Formal classroom systems are present in every learning center around the world, whether it is a developed or developing nation. The classroom environment is a significant, potent, and successful socialization tool where students from diverse backgrounds come together to learn (Raccoon gang, 2018). A positive learning environment can contribute to improved academic achievement, while a negative environment can hinder learning and lead to poor achievement. Therefore, creating a positive and supportive learning environment is essential for promoting student success. According to Alonso-Tapia and Ruiz-Díaz (2022) the classroom climate primarily consists of the impressions that students form based on their exposure to various learning contexts, as well as the resources and opportunities that are available in the setting. There are two main components to a classroom setting: the human element and the physical element. The human component of the classroom consists of the people who are there, such as the teachers and students, whereas the physical component consists of all the actual things that are in the room, such as the projector, books, computers, and blackboard. Generally speaking, it deals with how teachers and students connect with one another. This interactional pattern creates a specific setting that can be referred to as a learning condition, circumstance, or environment. This feature is sometimes referred to as the classroom's psycho-social environment (Malik and Asad, 2018). The relatedness of students with teachers and peers in the classroom is also a vital component for the psycho-social development of students, according to the social-cognitive model (Pekrun, 2018). Interacting with teachers and classmates in the classroom is a daily routine in a middle school student's life. These teacher-student and student-student relationships may induce positive activity-related emotions during the learning process (Peixoto, 2017; Forsblom, 2021). Building strong relationships with students,

setting clear expectations for the classroom, providing opportunities for social skill development, and delivering relevant content are all ways that educators can create this kind of atmosphere. When students believe that teachers value their opinions in a positive learning environment, they can take an increasingly active role in their education. In a positive learning environment, students feel comfortable voicing their opinions, taking calculated risks, asking questions, and overcoming challenges in their academic pursuits (Akomolafe and Veronica, 2015). Research has shown that a strong emotional connection between teachers and students and a consistently positive classroom environment can enhance students' motivation, overall well-being, class participation, satisfaction, and engagement in group projects and activities, while reducing their anxiety and sense of dread (Barr, 2016; MacLeod et al., 2018).

Students engaging in sympathetic and supportive interactions with peers characterize a socially engaged and productive classroom environment (Taherian et al., 2021). Certain behaviors, such as showing gratitude, smiling, and exchanging ideas and memories, form the foundation of student-student interactions and have the potential to positively impact learning outcomes and experiences (Elahi and Talezadeh, 2018a; Vranjes and Brone, 2021). It is important to emphasise the value of social connections in a supportive learning environment because learning and teaching occur both inside the classroom and between students and their teacher. However, if the classroom atmosphere is unpleasant, students' academic achievement could decrease (Lim et al., 2022). It has been discovered that ineffective teaching and improved student learning are hampered by a hostile classroom environment, unsupportive teachers, a lack of pedagogical expertise, and disruptive students (Ahmed et al, 2020).

Numerous studies have shown that a student's academic success is impacted by their family type, socioeconomic status, and the school environment. Research indicates that children from higher socioeconomic backgrounds tend to perform better academically, scoring higher on

tests and achieving better grades (OECD, 2019). Individuals from privileged backgrounds possess the ability to strategically use their knowledge, privileges, and resources to their advantage. This allows them to disproportionately take advantage of educational and extracurricular systems and opportunities, which in turn leads to better educational outcomes for students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds (Tompsett and Knoester, 2021; Alam and Forhad, 2022). Munir et al. (2023) propose that the relationship between academic achievement and socioeconomic status may be moderated by family involvement and school resources. Studies suggest that children in joint families experience more competition and peer comparison compared to those in nuclear families, potentially leading to disinterest in education and lower confidence in their abilities (Khalid et al., 2021). However, other research has found that parental involvement has a greater impact on children's academic success than home and school characteristics. Children's learning behaviours are more active when their parents are involved in their education, and their interest in learning is influenced by the quality of their schooling. This indicates that parental involvement in education may act as a mediator between higher family socioeconomic status and children's enthusiasm for learning (Li and Qiu, 2018). Additionally, Udayakumar et al. (2022) found that socioeconomic factors are linked to school choice, access to educational resources, and engagement in schooling, all of which impact children's academic achievement.

Theoretical framework

Researchers and educators have long been investigating the different elements, both contextual and personal, that affect students' academic achievement. Bronfenbrenner's offered one of the most well-known models in this area, the socio-ecological model, which incorporates all of these elements into a single model. Four levels of interaction patterns are classified under the model: micro, meso, exo, and macro (Bronfenbrenner's (1979, 1995a, 1995b). A youngster spends much of their time in the family, school, and neighbourhood (micro-level systems),

where they interact with others directly. Two micro-level systems interact with one another to form the meso-level system. Due to their close interactions within these levels, a number of studies have revealed a direct correlation between these micro- and meso-level systems and children's social and emotional development. The other two layers do not directly affect or include children; they are the macro-level (culture, policies) and the exo-level (parent job or working place, and their associations) (Donald, 2010). Empirical research has outlined several factors in Bronfenbrenner's socio-ecological model have an impact on children's academic achievement (Gustavsen, 2018; Otara and Hezekiah, 2021). The most emphasized factors, however, seem to be the school environment, family type and socioeconomic status (a micro-level system) (Finch and Finch, 2022). Studies have shown that a child's development is significantly influenced by the availability of educational resources and a supportive learning environment at home and at school (Nieuwenhuis and Hooimeijer, 2015). Some researchers suggest that a child's family type and socioeconomic status may have an equal impact on their academic success as other micro-level factors like the quality of the school and classroom. However, others argue that when combined with proper parenting, supportive peers, safe housing, and a positive school and neighborhood environment, socioeconomic status acts as a catalyst, improving children's academic achievement.

Study objectives

In developed nations a wide range of studies are conducted to examine the relationship between school environment, family type and family socioeconomic status (SES) on academic achievement. However, there is need of research studies in developing and less developed nations in the subject area. Therefore, the present study was conducted to determine the relationship between students' academic achievement and the classroom environment, taking into account the significant influence of other micro-level

systems including family socioeconomic status and family type.

Methodology

Design

The study followed a quantitative and cross sectional study design.

Sampling and sample

A multistage stratified random sampling technique was employed for the study. In the first stage, District Malakand was divided into two Tehsils. The Tehsils were then further divided into 28 Union Councils (UCs), with 5 urban and 23 rural UCs, in a ratio of 1:5 (Stage 2). Following this ratio, 2 urban and 10 rural UCs were selected (Stage 3). In the 4th stage, one government boy's school, one government girls' school, and one private school were purposively chosen from each UC for data collection. These 36 selected schools have a total enrollment of 7,952 students, and the required sample size is 448 (Chaudhry, 2009), which was then proportionally distributed to each school based on the total number of students.

Measurement of Variables

The classroom environment was measured on 10 items, the attributes for measurement of school environment was "Yes" and "No". The family socioeconomic status (SES) of the students was measured while considering parental education, family monthly income, and occupation/income source. Parental education was categorized into seven levels: 1=illiterate, 2=primary (five years of education), 3=middle (eight years of education), 4=secondary/matriculate (ten years of education), 5=intermediate (twelve years of education), 6=bachelor's degree (fourteen years of education), and 7=masters and above (sixteen years of education and above). Family monthly income was divided into three levels: 1=less than PRs. 15,000, 2=PRs. 15,001-30,000, and 3=above PRs. 30,000. Occupation/major income source was assessed on a four-level scale: 1=private job/business, 2=agriculture, 3=remittances and 4=government job. The maximum possible score for the SES scale was 14. Respondents scoring 7 or below were classified as Low Socioeconomic

status families, while those scoring above 7 were categorized as High Socioeconomic status families. The percentage of students' grades on their last exam was taken into account when assessing the academic achievement of students.

Data analysis

The data was analyzed using bivariate and multivariate level analysis. Chi-square tests and Kendall's Tau-c (Tc) tests were used to examine the strength and direction of the association between variables. The bivariate level analysis assessed the relationship between classroom environment and students' academic achievement. The multivariate level analysis observed the relationship between classroom environment and students' academic achievement based on students' family type and family socioeconomic status.

Ethical considerations

Before collecting data, the interview schedule was pretested. An authority letter was obtained from the District education departments (male and female), and verbal consent was obtained from the students. Students' confidentiality was ensured, and the respondents were free to terminate the interview at any time. Additionally, to respect cultural considerations, a trained female investigator was hired to collect data from female respondents.

Results

Association between classroom environment and students' academic achievement

Table 1 highlighted that the association of students' academic achievement was found significant and positive with enough space for free and comfortable movement of students in the classroom ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.322$), proper lighting and ventilation system ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.260$), sufficient seating arrangements ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.167$), and paint color in the classroom ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.159$). In addition, students' academic achievement were also significantly and positively associated with teachers listening to students easily ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.180$), giving individual attention by teachers ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.220$), arrangement of weekly or

monthly tests ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.236$), providing feedback to students ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.331$), students' participation in class ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.348$), and respect among students from different backgrounds and cultures ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.126$).

Association between classroom environment and students' academic achievement (controlling for respondents family socioeconomic background)

Table 2 represents the association between classroom environment and students' academic achievement based on the varied socioeconomic background of the students. The results indicated that the classroom environment was significantly and positively associated with academic achievement for students from higher economic status families ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.419$). Similarly, for the aforementioned variables the association was significant and positive for students from lower economic status families ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.323$). The entire table showed a significant and positive association between classroom environment and academic achievement for students of varied socioeconomic status ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.875$).

Association between classroom environment and students' academic achievement (controlling for respondents family type)

Table 3 highlights the association between classroom environment and students' academic achievement based on the family type of the students. The results indicate that classroom environment is significantly and positively associated with academic achievement for students from nuclear families ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.312$). Similarly, for the aforementioned variables the association was significant and positive for students from joint families ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.227$). The entire table shows a significant and positive association between classroom environment and academic achievement for students from various family types ($P < 0.05$, $T^c = 0.689$).

Discussion

The classroom environment is one of the most significant contributing factors to students' academic achievement. The classroom environment encompasses the physical environment as well as the social environment

provided to students. The classroom environment directly influences the mental capabilities and personality development of children, which in turn shapes their academic achievement. A positive classroom environment is characterized by traits that fulfill the physical, psychological, and social needs of students. In a positive classroom environment, students feel comfortable and openly share their thoughts. Such an experience motivates students towards education, leading to higher achievement in schools. Conversely, a non-conducive classroom environment has an adverse effect on students' educational attainments. Students feel relaxed and satisfied in a class where there is enough space between the rows, proper lighting and ventilation systems, and sufficient seating arrangements. Student satisfaction with the school and classroom environment is the most important element in the educational development of children. In schools, teachers often keep the windows closed, and the lights off to save electricity, resulting in poor air quality in the classroom. Similarly, small cost reductions in energy use cannot outweigh the detrimental effects on performance and health (Wargocki and Wyon, 2017). Students' perceptions of the classroom and their motivation to learn are shaped by factors such as furniture, lighting, ventilation, and décor, which ultimately affect their academic achievement (Sonerai and Wyse, 2017; Jin and Peng, 2022). In a similar vein, Lam et al. (2019) discovered that classroom lighting, visibility, and décor improve student motivation and pleasure while also stimulating creativity and learning, which improves the learning effect for students.

For effective teaching and learning, the response of the teacher is a very important part of the classroom environment. An effective teaching and learning environment requires teachers to easily listen to the students, give individual attention to students, regularly arrange weekly or monthly tests, provide feedback to students, allow pupils to participate actively in the teaching and learning, and ensure that students respect each other's opinions. Effective teachers promote a learning environment in the classroom by establishing working

relationships with students and engaging students in the teaching-learning process. Effective teachers emphasize participatory teaching methodologies and ensure student participation in class. Participation of students in class is related to creativity, cognitive development, improving communication skills, and active engagement in studies. A participatory teaching approach boosts student interaction with peers and teachers, improves students' motivation, enhances school engagement, increases regularity, and results in higher academic achievement. Through active engagement in the learning process, a classroom that prioritizes student participation, teacher feedback, and group discussions has been shown to enhance students' academic achievement (Orwat et al., 2018). Furthermore, good teacher-student communication promotes attendance (Hard & RaoShah, 2022) and enhances class discussions and activities (Tang et al., 2020; Xu & Qiu, 2022).

Selection of school type is linked with parental socioeconomic status. Parents with higher socioeconomic status are more likely to enroll their children in quality schools. Quality schools provide an enabling learning environment to students that are associated with quality results among students. When associating classroom environment with academic achievement, and controlling for the socioeconomic status of students' families, the study found variation in students' academic achievement. The findings indicated that while experiencing the same classroom environment, children from high socioeconomic status families secured better academic grades compared to children from low socioeconomic standing families. The home environments, educational settings, resources available to children, neighborhoods they live in, and schools they attend can all be influenced by family SES (Tompsett and Knoester, 2023). Amoo et al. (2018) found a direct correlation between children's educational attainment and their socioeconomic status. Students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds typically perform better because they were able to enroll in high-quality schools with excellent

classrooms, readily available learning resources, and other facilities that are essential for their development. Parenting style, school quality, school involvement, academic behaviour, and socioeconomic status are all interconnected. Academic behaviour may also play a role in the relationship between socioeconomic status and children's academic success. Children from lower socioeconomic backgrounds tend to have lower academic achievement due to the challenges their parents face in providing a high-quality home and school environment (Zhang, 2021).

Worldwide, nuclear and joint families are acknowledged as well-known family structures. In Pakistan, particularly in the study area, joint families are more prevalent; however, as society has developed, joint families are gradually being replaced by nuclear families. The study analysis showed that when children experienced the same classroom environment, a nuclear family system had a greater positive impact on academic achievement than a joint family system. The facts that children in nuclear families receive the best level of care during study periods, help with schoolwork, and quality time from their parents are all plausible explanations for the study's findings. In addition, in joint families, children's responsibilities are shared by all family members in addition to their parents. As a result, parents in joint families do not devote themselves entirely to their children's education. Thus, in contrast to joint families, parents of nuclear families appropriately focus on the quality of education provided by schools and are actively involved in their children's academic pursuits, resulting in higher academic achievement. Scholars' conclusions regarding the effects of various family types on students' academic achievement are incongruous. Rahma et al, (2023) findings run counter to the study's findings that students from joint families outperform those from nuclear families, with 88.7% of joint family students and 84.1% of nuclear family students achieving satisfactory results. Maharishi and Parameswari (2013), however, emphasized that a student's academic achievement is influenced by their home and school environments, regardless of the type of family.

Conclusions

Family and school attributes are key sources of shaping students' academic achievement. The present study was designed to examine the influence of classroom environment, family socioeconomic status, and family type on students' academic achievement. The study concluded that children perform better academically when they experience a positive and conducive physical and social environment in the classroom. The results illustrated that improved academic achievement is linked to the appropriate physical classroom environment, such as, a classroom characterized by enough space for the free and comfortable movement of students, proper lighting and ventilation systems, and sufficient seating arrangements. The results also showed that students' academic achievement is positively influenced by the social environment of the classroom, such as a classroom where teachers effectively engage students, give individual attention to students, provide feedback to students, regularly assess students, and establish a working relationship with students. Additionally, the results highlighted that while experiencing the same classroom environment, children from nuclear and higher socioeconomic status families performed better compared to students from lower socioeconomic standings and joint families. Thus, it was concluded that family socioeconomic status and family type are significant contributors to children's academic achievement, besides the classroom learning environment.

Recommendations

The classroom environment is crucial for students' educational outcomes. The government education department should regularly assess the quality of classrooms in both government and private schools. Additionally, the department should focus on providing refresher courses and training for teachers to improve their capacity to establish a working relationship with students and adopt effective teaching methods. Schools should also offer scholarship opportunities for students from low socioeconomic backgrounds.

Furthermore, federal policies for poverty eradication need to be updated to better support low-income families and ensure quality education for their children. It is important to mobilize charitable resources such as "Zakat" and "Ushr" to support the educational and financial needs of families with low socioeconomic status. These social security measures have strong religious endorsements and can be easily enacted.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed G, Faizi WUN, Akbar S (2020) Challenges of Novice Teachers and Strategies to Cope at Secondary Level. *Global Regional Review (V-i)*: 403-416. DOI:10.31703/grr.2020(v-i).44
- Akomolafe, C. O and Veronica O. A. (2015). The Classroom Environment: A Major Motivating Factor towards High Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in South West Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, Vol.6, No.34.
- Alam G. M., & Forhad M. A. R. (2022). What makes a difference for further advancement of engineers: socioeconomic background or education programs?. *Higher Education*, 83(6), 1259–1278. doi: 10.1007/s10734-021-00741-4.
- Alonso-Tapia, J., and Ruiz-Díaz, M. (2022). Student, teacher, and school factors predicting differences in classroom climate: a multilevel analysis. *Learn. Individ. Differ.* 94:102115. doi: 10.1016/j.lindif.2022.102111.
- Amoo, T. B., O. P. Adeyinka, and A. D. Aderibigbe. (2018). "Perceived effects of parental socio-economic status on students' academic performance among teachers in Odeda Local Government, Ogun State, Nigeria," *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 254–264.
- Barr, J. J. (2016). *Developing a Positive Classroom Climate*. Manhattan: IDEA Centers, 1–9.

- Bronfenbrenner U. The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design. Harvard university press. 1979.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1995a). The bio ecological model from a life course perspective: Reflections of a participant observer. In P Moen, GH Elder & K Luscher (eds). Examining lives in context: Perspectives on the ecology of human development. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1995b). Developmental ecology through space and time: a future perspective. In P Moen, GH Elder & K Luscher (eds). "Examining lives in context: Perspectives on the ecology of human development. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- Donald D., Lazarus S., Lolwana, P. Educational Psychology in social context: Ecosystem applications. Southern Africa. Cape Town: Oxford University Press, 2010. [cited 2018 March 15]. Available from: <http://resjournals.com/journals/educational-research-journal/2017%20E/DU/July/Kudzai%20and%20Moses.pdf>.
- Elahi S. M., and Talezadeh, N. (2018a). Is transparency an illusion? An idiodynamic assessment of teacher and peers' reading of nonverbal communication cues of foreign language enjoyment. *J. Intercult. Commun. Res.* 47, 188–206. doi: 10.1080/17475759.2018.1453527.
- Finch H., Finch M. E. H. The Relationship of National, School, and Student Socioeconomic Status With Academic Achievement: A Model for Programme for International Student Assessment Reading and Mathematics Scores. *Front. Educ.* 2022; 7: 857451. DOI: 10.3389/feduc.2022.857451.
- Forsblom L, Peixoto F, Mata L. Perceived classroom support: longitudinal effects on students' achievement emotions. *Learn Individ Differ.* 2021;85(3):101959. doi:10.1016/j.lindif.2020.101959
- Gustavsen A. Gender differences in academic achievement: A matter of contextual classroom influence. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education.* 2018; 8(1): 1-20. DOI: [10.5861/ijrse.2018.2013](https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2018.2013).
- Hard, B. M., RaoShah, T. (2022). Developing collaborative thinkers: Rethinking how we define, teach, and assess class participation. *Teaching of Psychology*, 49, 176–184. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0098628320986953>.
- Harinarayanan, S., and Pazhanivelu, G. "Impact of School Environment on Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students at Vellore Educational District." *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2018, pp. 13–19. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2529402>.
- Jin, S., and Peng, L. (2022) Classroom perception in higher education: The impact of spatial factors on student satisfaction in lecture versus active learning classrooms. *Front. Psychol.* 13:941285. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.941285.
- Khalid, A., Painsa Khan, A., Mangan, S., Kumar, S., Golani, S., & Aqeel Zaidi, K. (2021). Joint Family or Nuclear Family: The Youth's Perspective. *Asian Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies.* <https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.500.2021.81.1.6>.
- Lam, E. W. M., Chan, D. W. M., and Wong, I. (2019). The architecture of built pedagogy for active learning—A case study of a university campus in Hong Kong. *Buildings* 9:230. doi: 10.3390/buildings9110230.
- Li, Z., Qiu, Z. How does family background affect children's educational achievement? Evidence from Contemporary China. *J. Chin. Sociol.* 5, 13 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40711-018-0083-8>.
- Lim, F. V., Toh, W., and Nguyen, T. T. H. (2022). Multimodality in the English language classroom: a systematic review of literature. *Linguist. Educ.* 69:101048. doi: 10.1016/j.linged.2022.101048.

- MacLeod, J., Yang, H. H., Zhu, S., and Shi, Y. (2018). Technological factors and student-to-student connected classroom climate in cloud classrooms. *J. Educ. Comput.* 56:826847.
- Maharishi R, Parameswari J. Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Study Involvement among Adolescents. *IJEPR*. 2013;2(4):30–36.
- Malik, R. H., and Asad A. R. 2018. . Effect of Classroom Learning Environment on Students' Academic Achievement in Mathematics at Secondary Level. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, Vol. 40, No. 2 pp. 207.
- Munir, J., Faiza, M., Jamal, B., Daud, S., & Iqbal, K. (2023). The Impact of Socioeconomic Status on Academic Achievement. *Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 3(2), 695-705. <https://doi.org/10.54183/jssr.v3i2.308>
- Nieuwenhuis J. Hooimeijer P. The association between neighborhoods and educational achievement, a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of housing and the built environment: HBE*. 2015; 31(2): 321–347. DOI: 10.1007/s 10901-015-9460-7.
- OECD. (2019). *PISA 2018 Results (Volume II): Where All Students Can Succeed*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
- Orwat J., Kumaria S., Spira M., Boyle L., Besinger A. (2018). Class participation as a pedagogical tool in social work education. *Social Work Education*, 37(3), 361–377. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02615479.2017.1401601>
- Otara A., Hezekiah O. School organizational factors as predictors of student achievement: Principals' perspective. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Studies*. 2021; 3 (1): 24-36. DOI: 10.29103/ijevs.v3i1.3373.
- Peixoto F, Sanches C, Mata L, Monteiro V. “How do you feel about math?”: relationships between competence and value appraisals, achievement emotions and academic achievement. *Eur J Psychol Educ*. 2017;32(3):385–405. doi:10.1007/s10212-016-0299-4
- Pekrun R. Control-value theory: a social-cognitive approach to achievement emotions. In: Liem GAD, McInerney DM, editors. *Big Theories Revisited 2: A Volume of Research on Sociocultural Influences on Motivation and Learning*. Charlotte, NJ: Information Age Publishing; 2018:162–190.
- Raccoon gang (2018) What Makes Good Learning Environment. Accessed 28/09/2019 from <https://raccoongang.com/blog/what-makes-good-learning-environment/06/04/2018>
- Rahman, S., Munam, A.M., Hossain, A. et al. (2023). Socio-economic factors affecting the academic performance of private university students in Bangladesh: a cross-sectional bivariate and multivariate analysis. *SN Soc Sci*, 3(26). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43545-023-00614-w>
- Singh SP, Malik S, Singh P. 2016. Factors affecting academic performance of students, *PJIR*. 5(4):176-178. DOI:10.36106/paripex
- Sonerl, P. A., and Wyse, S. A. (2017). A SCALE-UP mock-UP: comparison of student learning gains in high-and low-tech active-learning environments. *CBE-Life Sci. Educ*. 16:ar12. doi: 10.1187/cbe.16-07-0228
- Taherian, T., Fazilatfar, A. M., and Mazdayasna, G. (2021). Joint growth trajectories of trait emotional intelligence subdomains among L2 language learners: estimating a second-order factor-of-curves model with emotion perception. *Front. Psychol*. 12. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.720945.
- Tang, L., Li S., Auden, E., Dhuey E. (2020). Who benefits from regular class participation? *The Journal of Economic Education*, 51(3–4), 243–256. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220485.2020.1804502>.
- Tompsett J, Knoester C. (2021). The making of a college athlete: High school experiences,

socioeconomic advantages, and the likelihood of playing college sports. *Sociology of Sport Journal*.39(2):129–40.

Tompsett, J., Knoester, C. (2023). Family socioeconomic status and college attendance: A consideration of individual-level and school-level pathways. *PLoS One*.11;18(4):e0284188. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0284188.

Udayakumar, K., Shanmugan R., Arumugam, S. R, 2022. SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS IMPACT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS – A REGRESSION ANALYSIS , *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, Vol. 6, No. 6, 5612 – 5626.

Vranjes, J., and Brone, G. (2021). Interpreters as laminated speakers: gaze and gesture as

interpersonal deixis in consecutive dialogue interpreting. *J. Pragmat.* 181, 83–99. doi: 10.1016/j.pragma.2021.05.008.

Wargoeki, P., and D. Wyon. 2017. “Ten Questions Concerning Thermal and Indoor Air Quality Effects on the Performance of Office Work and Schoolwork.” *Building and Environment* 112: 359–66.

Xu, Y., Qiu, X. (2022). Necessary but problematic: Chinese university English teachers’ perceptions and practices of assessing class participation. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 27, 841–858. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2020.1747424>.

Zhang, P. P. (2021). How Do Disadvantaged Students Become Academically Resilient? The Joint Effect of Family Social Capital and School Quality. *Educ. Econ.*37:39–49.

Table 1
Association between *classroom environment* and academic achievement

Independent variable (<i>Classroom Attributes</i>)	Dependent variable	Statistics χ^2 , (P-Value) & T ^c
Student can move freely and comfortably in your classroom	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=45.693(0.000)$ T ^c =0.322
There is adequate light and ventilation system in your classroom	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=26.206 (0.000)$ T ^c =0.260
There is ample seating arrangements for students in your classroom	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=13.647 (0.002)$ T ^c =0.167
The paint color in your classroom is not disturbing which helps you to focus on the teachers' discussion	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=17.304 (0.001)$ T ^c =0.159
Teachers can easily listen to the students in your classroom	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=27.460(0.020)$ T ^c =0.180
Teacher gives Individual attention to students in your classroom	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=14.287(0.003)$ T ^c =0.220
Teachers arrange weekly or monthly test for students in your classroom	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=9.943(0.000)$ T ^c =0.236
Teachers Provide feedback to students about their weaknesses in your classroom	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=69.261(0.000)$ T ^c =0.331
Teachers allow pupils to participate actively in the teaching and learning in your classroom	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=33.261(0.000)$ T ^c =0.348
Students from different backgrounds and cultures respect each other view point in your classroom	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=12.943(0.02)$ T ^c =0.126

Table 2

Association between classroom environment and children academic achievement (controlling for respondents family socioeconomic background)

Family socioeconomic status	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Statistics χ^2 , (P-Value) & T ^c	Statistics χ^2 , (P-Value) & T ^c for entire table
High SES	Classroom environment	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=26.163$ (0.001) T ^c =0.419	$\chi^2=46.381$ (0.001) T ^c =0.875
Low SES	Classroom environment	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=24.596$ (0.030) T ^c =0.323	

Table 3

Association between classroom environment and children academic achievement (controlling for respondents family type)

Family socioeconomic status	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Statistics χ^2 , (P-Value) & T ^c	Statistics χ^2 , (P-Value) & T ^c for entire table
Nuclear Family	Classroom environment	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=23.234$ (0.001) T ^c =0.312	$\chi^2=44.116$ (0.010) T ^c =0.689
Joint Family	Classroom environment	Academic achievement	$\chi^2=25.766$ (0.030) T ^c =0.227	